

INFORMATION LITERACY IN TEACHING PHILIPPINE LITERATURE AND THE READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE 11 ABM STUDENTS

DARREN A. TENORIO

17-fs-eng-270@lspu.edu.ph

ORCID No. 0000-0003-4077-3828

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The Philippines finished dead last in reading comprehension on the recent Programme for International Student Assessment. The successful countries had a great deal of expertise in terms of information literacy. This study focused in determining the effect of information literacy instruction in teaching Philippine Literature to the reading comprehension of students. Grade 11 ABM FAITH Fidelis Senior High students were chosen as respondents of the study. This used quasi-experimental design specifically quantitative methods in questionnaire with the components of reading comprehension in literal, interpretive and evaluative level as the data-gathering instrument. It is consisted of the pre-test and post-test items given to the experimental group who undergone literature classes with the integration of information literacy instruction. Also, same items were given to the control group who undergone literature classes with the usual modular instruction. This study undergone treatment among the experimental and control group in three lesson sessions respectively. The result revealed no significant difference between the pre and post-test scores of the students in reading comprehension in terms of literal, interpretive and evaluative level before and after using modular instruction. However, after using information literacy instruction, it was found out that there is a significant difference between the pre and post-test scores of the students in reading comprehension in terms of interpretive level. Hence, no significant difference as to literal and evaluative level. Teachers may put an emphasis on improving higher-order thinking skills through improving reading comprehension on the evaluative level. More so, teachers can also consider giving more opportunities for the students to express themselves, reasoning out in the class, allowing them to display their judgments. Teachers may integrate information literacy instruction in teaching literature to improve the interpretive comprehension of the students. Also, teachers may highlight evaluative questions when discussing literary text or any text linked with comprehension.

Keywords: information literacy, reading comprehension, quasi-experimental, Fidelis Senior High Philippines